

Environmental problems and causes and problems of their origin

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Аннотация: *В этой статье пойдет речь о глобальных экологических проблемах в мире, с которыми в настоящее время сталкивается человек, и причинах их возникновения, а также о способах решения этих проблем.*

Ключевые слова: *наука, экология, природа, проблемы, причины, реформы.*

Abstract: *This article talks about global environmental problems facing people today and their causes, as well as solutions to these problems.*

Key words: *Science, ecology, nature, problems, causes, reforms.*

The technological revolution of Science marked a new stage in the relationship of society and nature from the nature of quality. This stage is characterized by the extraordinary need to master natural resources at an unprecedented level of use of existing resources on the planet. The scientific technical revolution brought to the surface technical and technological tools that were not previously known. As a result of the revolution in science and Technology, man reached a new level in freedom in the attitude to nature, as a result of which he managed to curb the many forces that he had not bought himself before.

Science the intense progress of the technique has led to the fact that at the moment the range of human influence on nature and the expansion of scale has led to the fact that changes are taking place in the natural environment under the

influence of anthropogenic factors. And such changes are ruining the material foundations of life. The environment that surrounds man, making society unsuitable for life activities, threatens the extinction of our planet. The problem of preserving the means of living; becoming the subject of the century, the world community is in the spotlight. Pollution of the environment as a result of production processes is not only an absolute obvious threat to future generations, but it has also come to the brink of social destruction in the present itself.

Science clearly demonstrates that the technological revolution has led to an increase in social influence on the nature that surrounds us, which has led to an increase in the influence of nature on society. The intensification of production processes taking place necessitates the attraction of natural resources to the national economy in ever-growing quantities. With this, it also enhances the direct dependence of society on nature. During the current scientific technical revolution, the possibilities of human use of the riches of nature are greatly expanded. At the same time, the dangerous harmful effect of industrial production on nature and the environment is greatly increased. In the next 100 years, humanity increased its energy wealth by a thousand times. This allows him to exert a serious influence on nature and the consequences of which extend far. In the course of the science technology revolution, these indicators will grow again. The total volume of goods and services in developed countries is now 2 times every 15 years.

Accordingly, the amount of waste from agricultural activities that contaminate the atmosphere, water bodies, soil is also increasing by 2 times. Production takes 100 conditional units from nature, but uses only 3-4 parts. the remainder is disposed of into the environment in the form of contaminated matter and waste. In industrially developed countries, 30 tons of substances per capita are extracted from nature every year, of which in some cases 1-1.5% fall into the desired product form, while the rest often become waste, which is also dangerous

for nature. The technological revolution of science has led to the fact that, firstly, the processes of biosphere destruction are accelerated, and secondly, new manifestations of matter and energy of the biosphere are introduced, which do not appear natural in nature: thirdly, the forces and laws of nature are increasingly moving in New Directions. If the requirements of domestication in the relations of society with nature put New-new problems before humanity, then the problems of bora-bora also blurred. Now, the main areas of influence on the environment are the industrialization of the development of scientific technology and the growth of industry at a high pace, the high level of material consumption. In the following years, a whole group of previously unknown diseases arose and were identified, with specific epidemiological and practical infectious diseases, prevention of complex is genetic diseases, endocrine, allergic and poisoning diseases, including poisoning that is exacerbated by an increase in the mass of previously absent chemicals-allergic diseases are among them. Thus, the environment played an important role among the factors that determine the health of the population and human development in general. When conditions are created to improve and strengthen health, its effects can be digested.

Historical forms of unity of people in a social group Family, production team, professional group, Nation, State, socio-economic formation cannot be understood human ecology without deeply striking the social system of relations and relations at different levels. The ecological situation is directly related to the level of development of specific forms of interaction of society and nature in various socio-economic formations. The relationship between the organism and the environment occurs on the basis of adaptation. I.P.Pavlov believes that the most general description of the creature is that it responds with its specific activity not only to external observers, but also to other observers in contact during its separate period. That is, the living being divides into the ability to adapt.

This feature is manifested in different ways, you should not look at it only in a narrow sense. The large group of animal species also adapts poorly and actively to weather conditions. From this point of view, adaptation is such a process that it also gives organisms a taste for the environment that surrounds it. Throughout its history, human society interacts with the environment without interruption. In doing so, it adapts steadily to the environment. But this adaptation will have an active character. Gradually improving the environment and lifestyle around oneself is the same active form in human adaptation. A person exerts his influence on the environment through Labor.

It not only separates the Society of social production from nature, but also connects society with the rest of nature. Unlike other living organisms, the same production of nature modifier activity is specific and human-specific activity. A person forms his environment around him. Nature and man constitute living beings. Society cannot live in its inorganic body except nature. Foreign social practitioners, social hygienists assess the impact of the technological progress of science on the fate of mankind, arguing that science and technology in itself bring humanity to an electronic Paradise. In it, all the contradictions of the present will be eliminated, people and under the influence of the development of the Māori will acquire the highest moral qualities. At the next time, with the overall rapid development of the new technique, there is also a significant shift in the provision of safety. But as all aspects of life are intensively Technical, a sharp increase in the number of technical equipment, the effective limits of the protection of the natural conditions of their life for its health and life are seriously tightening.

This conflict, according to its source, is not related to the character of production relations and overlaps the emergence in every society that widely uses the technique. But the character of production relations shows its influence on the forms and methods of resolving these conflicts. drawing conclusions from the past,

it is necessary to establish a social examination of scientific technical and engineering projects to a truly significant and enormous scale. It is necessary to attract the general public to this work. It is then that it is possible to greatly reduce and, moreover, completely eliminate environmental and other defects that can occur as a result of uncontrolled development of projects and their implementation. In the current period, when the problems of Ecology and conservation have become serious, bringing the relation in the middle of nature and society to balance is one of the main tasks. The problem of interaction between nature, man and society is one of the main issues. Nature is the living environment of society, the source of satisfying its material and spiritual needs. Society is a higher stage in the development of nature and has a special social meaning. Two parts of one whole matter, in which nature and society are inextricably linked, are a kind of social ecosystem. In the system of interaction of nature and society, man occupies a central place. Put an end at the same time, both nature and nature are an integral part of society and have a social biological essence. The exchange of matter and energy is the basis of the existence of nature. Society, in which matter is a high form of movement, lives and develops as a separate part of nature. At different stages of the development of society, his attitude towards nature was also changing. In the primitive community system, mankind did not have a significant impact on nature. the rise of Agriculture and animal husbandry in the system of slavery was the reason for the increased influence on nature. As a result of the improvement of the means of labor in the feudalism regime, the increase in the number of inhabitants, the sphere of human influence and image grew. With the decision of the capitalist socio-economic system, the development of Science and technology, the emergence of industry, transport, the rapid assimilation of Natural Resources brought to a high level of influence on nature. The problem of pollution of the environment with harmful emissions has arisen. A kind of anthropogenic

exchange of matter and energy arose between nature and society. The exchange of anthropogenic substances, that is, the extraction of raw materials from nature in love and the disposal of harmful waste products into the environment, caused a long-standing imbalance between nature and society. In the development of the relationship of nature and society, biogenic, anthropogenic and man-made (non-homogeneous) stages are distinguished. A strong anthropogenic impact of the state of the indigenous environment on human-influenced, living and inanimate components creates environmental problems. Local, regional and Universal environmental problems can be distinguished. Local, Islet, Chernobyl regional environmental situations have arisen in individual districts, where some large cities, industrial centers are located. The problem of ozone holes, acidic Badgers, desertification, pollution of the World Ocean and others are universal environmental problems.

A sharp increase in areas with an environmental crisis on Earth suggests that the threat of an environmental crisis is real. If all the necessary measures are not taken to solve environmental problems in the next 30-40 years, an environmental crisis can become inevitable. The proportional development of nature and society is called coevolution. This leads to a crisis when the images of development are not consistent. The influence of society on nature should be put in order. Ecology is understood as the biological science that studies the relationship of organisms with each other and with the environment.

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